

Million of Erasmus Grants

Designing the MEGA blueprint

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The vision of the Million of Erasmus Grants (MEGA) project is to facilitate the management of Erasmus+ grants at the university level and to develop a digital tool to ensure that these grants are paid to students in terms of both accuracy and time. It aims to develop the best possible tool to facilitate the management of Erasmus+ grants, taking into account the national and local contexts of HEIs throughout the Erasmus+ grant process. In order to design a valid and applicable system for all, the differences in grant management must first be identified.

In the first phase of the implementation of the project, a survey was disseminated among students and International Relations Offices (IROs) to better understand the challenges in managing grant payments and the possible solutions.

The second phase of MEGA was the core part of the work. Partners set out to build a blueprint that will enable higher education institutions (HEIs) to speed up the grant distribution process. This blueprint will be made available to all European universities wishing to implement it.

Based on our survey results, this document should address the specifications of the MEGA blueprint.

2. Summary of the survey results

MEGA partners disseminated two surveys: one for students and one for IRO.

Their analysis shows that students:

- Ask for clear and transparent communication. They want to know exactly how long they will be supported and the terms and conditions of their grant.
- Prefer to receive the grant before their Erasmus program begins, or at the very beginning of their mobility. Indeed, this appears to be the time when they need the money the most. Several respondents noted that delays in receiving the grant can cause financial difficulties for students.
- Support a more standardized and unified system across Europe.
- Would benefit from a more simplified grant management system with fewer procedures and less bureaucracy. This would indeed make it easier for students with fewer opportunities to apply to the program. An automated system that pre-fills basic information could be helpful in this regard.
- Propose the payment to be split into multiple instalments to help them manage their expenses.

Suggestions from respondents:

From the answers provided, it seems that there are several common suggestions to reach an ideal grant process:

1. Clear and easy-to-understand steps and concrete timelines.
2. Transparency, efficiency and easy-to-use grant management system.
3. Assistance, with individual support.
4. Payment of the grant before departure, preferably in one or two instalments, to cover expenses such as rent, travel, and other needs.
5. Monthly payments of Erasmus grants to help students manage their financial needs.
6. Recognition of the full length of the Erasmus period and easier demonstration of the time spent abroad.
7. Predictable payment that is delivered on time, preferably before the mobility (for the first instalment) or in the middle of the experience (for the second instalment).
8. Creating a calculator that enables students to know the expected amount of the grant.
9. Availability of the grant when the student confirms the decision to leave and the first part of the grant should be paid before starting the mobility or just a few days later.
10. Pop-ups with explanations when the cursor is hovering over a question mark on the online platform to help students with the application process.
11. Standardization of the grant process and base it on flat rates per month.
12. Flexibility: Participants recommended a flexible system that allows students to decide when to receive their grants and to make changes if necessary.
13. A centralized system that would make it easier for them to submit their applications and manage their grants.

Definitions:

The MEGA project aims at developing an API that will be available to all European universities.

The API, or application programming interface, is a set of defined rules that enable different applications to communicate with each other. It acts as an intermediary layer that processes data transfers between systems, letting companies open their application data and functionality to external third-party developers, business partners, and internal departments within their companies (<https://www.ibm.com/topics/api>).

Recommendations:

Starting from the burdens found in the first part of the project and from the suggestions made by the different stakeholders, we describe here the specifications and functionalities that should be included in the blueprint, where possible.

1. The platform should show a timeline that makes the advancement of the grant process clear.
2. This timeline should be easily readable: each step should be indicated with green dots when completed, yellow ones when ongoing, and red ones when the task is incomplete.
3. Under each dot, there should be an indication of who is responsible for each task.
4. We should include all the payment steps of the mobility grant in it.
5. The platform should be flexible: Each institution chooses the relevant part that applies to it, and in which order.
6. The platform should automatically calculate the grant based on the information provided (length of the stay, destination, etc.) and be visible to both students and IRO staff.
7. The grant agreement is automatically generated and pre-filled.
8. There should be a way to assist students and IROs in using it. It can be by means of pop-ups on the cursor.
9. The MEGA solution is a connection between mobility applications (dashboard, OLA, third-party solutions, in-house developed solutions etc.) and financial ones.
10. Each institution needs to declare at which step the payment is automatically made.
11. The platform should include a series of internal validations: at least from the IRO and the financial office.

The main idea is to create an API that communicates, on one hand with the current mobility tools used by the HEIs (Dashboard, MoveOn, Mobility Online, etc.) and on other EU tools for mobility, such as OLA, and on the other hand with the financial tools used by HEIs.

With the MEGA blueprint, each HEI is then responsible for building its own bridges.

Functionalities:

The MEGA solution will gather information from the mobility platform and send it to the financial platform of the institution. This information will allow MEGA to automatically edit the grant agreement and calculate the grant.

The MEGA solution will allow each HEI to set up the trigger point when the grant should be paid to the student, for instance at the confirmation of arrival for the first instalment. When this information is sent by the mobility management tools, or uploaded into MEGA, a connection is then automatically created with the institution's financial tool and the grant is automatically transferred to the students.

Alternatively, an Excel file can be imported with all necessary data.

Offline = the connection that needs to be done

- Connecting the finance application to the MEGA timeline
- Connecting the mobility management tool to the timeline
- Connecting the mobility management tool to the finance application
- Connecting the timeline to the Erasmus+ app? Further steps to be discussed with the European Commission

☰	[G01Q02] > Registration in a m...	■
☰	[G01Q03] > Verification	□
☰	[G01Q04] > OLA	□
☰	[G01Q05] > Editing of the GA	□
☰	[G01Q07] > GA- Student signa...	□
☰	[G01Q08] > GA- Institution sign...	□
☰	[G01Q09] > Confmation of arri...	■
☰	[G01Q10] > Half of mobility	■
☰	[G01Q11] > Transcript of Reco...	■
☰	[G01Q12] > Confirmation of ...	■

For IROs, the possibility to choose which steps to show in the timeline, according to its own regulations. The possibility to change the order of the different elements of the timeline.

Example of a timeline at the end of the mobility: all the dots are green. The bigger ones are the trigger points for the grant payment (to be chosen by each institution).

Below is a non-exhaustive list of all steps to be included and visible on the timeline:

- Registration on the mobility platform (red= not done by the student, orange = done waiting for control, green = control done)
- OLA (red = not done by students, orange = in process, green = validated by both partners + link to the OLA platform)
- Grant Agreement (red = not edited yet, orange = edited to be signed, green = fully signed, when orange = need to indicate which signature is missing, student of HEI)
- The first payment (red = mobility file not completed, orange = completed waiting for control, green = payment sent when red = link to mobility management tool to indicate what document is missing when orange = need to indicate what control is needed - IRO of financial office)
- Confirmation of arrival (red = not done by students, orange = done but waiting for control, green = validated)
- Half of mobility (notification to all stakeholders student, host and home institution), each institution can choose when this mark is
- Transcrit of records (red = added by student, orange = waiting for confirmation, green = confirmed)
- Confirmation of departure (red = not done by student, orange = done by student, waiting for confirmation, green = validated)
- Final payment (red = mobility file not completed, orange = completed waiting for control, green = payment sent when red = link to mobility management tool to indicate what document is missing when orange = need to indicate what control is needed - IRO of financial office)

Each institution can freely add additional steps, while also merging others (i.e., the second payment cannot be processed until the first payment is complete).

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